

Appendix 3: The NEE actions at the governmental level in the US¹

Legislation and Regulation by the US Government about Engineering Ethics

Through laws, regulations, and professional standards, federal and state governments have helped maintain the integrity of the engineering profession and ensure that engineers act in the public's best interests. Some of the key ways in which governments have influenced engineering ethics legislation in the US include:

(1) **Laws requiring engineers to be licensed:** Many states have enacted laws requiring engineers to obtain a license to practice, and these licensing requirements often include ethical standards that must be met. State licensing boards are responsible for enforcing these standards and investigating complaints of ethical violations.

(2) **Engineering codes of conduct:** One of the most significant pieces of legislation related to engineering ethics is the NSPE Code of Ethics. While the NSPE Code of Ethics is not a law, many state licensing boards have incorporated it into their regulations and require engineers to abide by it. Also, many state engineering licensing boards have adopted codes of ethics that govern the professional behavior of engineers. For example, the Texas Board of Professional Engineers (TBPE) has established a code of conduct that requires engineers to uphold high standards of professional conduct and to avoid conflicts of interest (Texas Board of Professional Engineers and Land Surveyors, 2023). Other states, such as California and New York, have similar codes of ethics enforced by their respective licensing boards.

(3) **The requirement of engineering codes of conduct for engineers working on federally funded projects:** For instance, according to Federal Acquisition Regulation (FAR), "Contractors should have a written code of business ethics and conduct. To promote compliance with such a code of business ethics and conduct, contractors should have an employee business ethics and compliance training program and an internal control system." (FAR, 2023).

(4) **Accreditation rules for engineering education:** As mentioned above, the ABET requires engineering programs to provide "an ability to recognize ethical and professional responsibilities in engineering situations and make informed judgments, which must consider the impact of engineering solutions in global, economic, environmental, and societal contexts." (ABET, 2023)

¹ This text is an appendix of the paper "A Comparative Institutional Analysis of Engineering Ethics in the Netherlands and the United States".

(5) Laws addressing specific issues: Several states have enacted laws and regulations that address specific ethical issues in engineering. For example, California has a law that requires engineers to report unsafe working conditions and environmental hazards (California Business and Professions Code, Section 6730).

(6) Laws for promoting specific ethical conduct: Several federal laws and regulations have been enacted to promote ethical conduct in engineering. For example, the False Claims Act (2023) penalizes individuals who submit false claims for payment to the federal government, including claims related to engineering work. Another example is the Whistle-Blowers Protection Act (1989), which protects employees who report violations of the law, including ethical violations, from retaliation by their employers.

Interaction of governments with professional engineering organizations in the US

(1) Accreditation and licensing: The federal government recognizes accreditation organizations that establish and maintain standards for engineering education, such as the Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET). ABET is recognized by the US Department of Education and the Council for Higher Education Accreditation (CHEA) as a reliable authority for the accreditation of engineering programs. Moreover, government authorities work in conjunction with engineering professional organizations to carry out tasks relating to the licensing of the engineering profession, such as the operations of the state licensing boards and their exams.

(2) Financial support: The US government funds engineering ethics initiatives through agencies like the Department of Defense (DoD) and the NSF. Developing and implementing ethics education programs, including curriculum development, training materials, and workshops; creating and publishing ethical guidelines and codes of conduct; conducting research projects; and developing case studies highlighting the ethical challenges and dilemmas engineers face are a few examples of these programs. Furthermore, the government offers tax incentives to companies that invest in research and development, which can help professional engineering organizations.

(3) Regulatory oversight: The federal government oversees professional engineering organizations through the National Council of Examiners for Engineering and Surveying (NCEES). NCEES develops and administers the licensure examinations for engineers and serves as a central clearinghouse for engineering licensure information in the United States.

(4) Partnership and collaboration: The government partners with professional engineering organizations to advance shared goals, such as promoting innovation and sustainability. For example, the US Department of Energy collaborates with organizations

such as the American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME) and the National Society of Professional Engineers (NSPE) to develop energy-efficient technologies and improve the efficiency of the nation's energy infrastructure.

Supporting academic programs (research and education)

(1) NSF: The NSF is an independent federal organization that supports engineering and science in the United States. The NSF was created by Congress in 1950 to advance science, improve national health, wealth, and welfare, and secure the country's security. Since this field's inception, governments have supported it well through this organization. For instance, with the help of the NSF at the end of the 1970s, the first teams composed of engineers and philosophers were formed. In fact, with its support, the NSF involved philosophers in engineering ethics issues. The first textbooks were written through these supports (Mitcham & Briggie, 2009). According to Didier (2012), this incident marked a turning point in developing engineering ethics.

(2) National Academy of Engineering (NAE): The NAE, which was established in 1964, is an organization that offers engineering leadership in support of the country. This organization is a National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine division. It is governed by the congressional act of incorporation that created the National Academy of Sciences. Following this charter, the NAE is mandated "whenever called upon by any department or agency of the government, to investigate, examine, experiment, and report upon any subject of science or art." The NAE's objective is to enhance the welfare and prosperity of the country by offering unbiased advice on issues relating to engineering and technology, encouraging a vibrant engineering profession, and raising public awareness of engineering. The NAE has been actively involved in promoting ethics education in engineering. In his lecture in 2001 at a meeting, the NAE president said that the NAE could lead the discussion on engineering ethics in the twenty-first century (Wulf, 2002). It has published numerous reports and guidelines on ethical behavior in engineering, such as the book "On Being a Scientist: A Guide to Responsible Conduct in Research" and the report "Engineering Ethics: Concepts and Cases." In 2004 and 2005, NAE published two reports on engineering characteristics in the year 2020 and engineering education in the light of that vision, which emphasized the ethics of engineers (Mitcham, 2009). With support from the NSF, the NAE organized the workshop "Ethics Education and Scientific and Engineering Research in 2009 (Hoffmann & Borenstein, 2014). In addition, the NAE has provided grants to support the development of ethics curricula for engineering programs. Also, the National Academy of Engineering recently sponsored a special workshop on "Emerging Technologies and Ethical Issues in Engineering" (Deborah & Jameson, 2008).

(3) Accreditation bodies: Accreditation bodies such as the Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET) have included ethics education as a requirement for engineering programs to obtain accreditation. Since the middle of the 1980s, the ABET has increased the requirements for engineering programs to incorporate professional ethics instruction. This resulted in the introduction of the Engineering Criteria 2000, which was published in 1997 and made it mandatory to include courses about the ethical obligations of engineers. ABET's Engineering Accreditation Commission (EAC) requires that engineering programs "demonstrate that their graduates have an understanding of professional and ethical responsibility."

(4) Federal agencies such as the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and the Department of Energy (DOE) have also supported engineering ethics education. For instance, NASA's Office of the Chief Engineer has funded initiatives to develop ethics curricula for aerospace engineering students. The DOE has provided grants to support research on ethical issues related to nuclear engineering.

Establishment of regulatory bodies (such as state engineering boards, National Institute of Standards and Technology, and NSF)

The involvement of regulatory bodies like the NSPE, coupled with the enactment of legislation and codes of ethics, has helped to establish a framework for ethical conduct in the engineering profession in the US.

Act against violations of engineers

As the engineering profession is regulated by state licensing boards in the United States, violations of the NSPE code of conduct can result in disciplinary action by state licensing boards. For instance, in 2012, the Illinois Department of Financial and Professional Regulation revoked the license of an engineer who had submitted false information on his application for licensure. In 2015, the Texas Board of Professional Engineers revoked the license of an engineer who had signed off on the structural plans for a Dallas Cowboys practice facility that collapsed, injuring several people. The consequences of these violations can be severe, including fines, suspension or revocation of licensure, and even criminal charges in some cases. For instance, In 2018, California revoked the license of a structural engineer who had falsified seismic test results for over a decade. The engineer was also fined and ordered to pay restitution to affected clients. In 2017, an engineer in Massachusetts was sentenced to two years in prison for his role in a scheme to falsify test results on concrete used in a significant construction project. The engineer had accepted

bribes to certify that the concrete met strength requirements, even though it had not been adequately tested.